

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinterac-
tions/arthropodEasyCaptureAMNH
hash://md5/eae87918c1dffbb12bee888d9df95f3b

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/arthropodEasyCaptureAMNH, has fingerprint hash://md5/eae87918c1dffbb12bee888d9df95f3b, is 54.9MiB in size and contains 709,968 interactions with 5 unique types of associations (e.g., interactsWith) between 8,343 primary taxa (e.g., *Lysiphlebus Lysiphlebus*) and 9,207 associated taxa (e.g., *Melilotus officinalis*). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Collaborative databasing of North American bee collections within a global informatics network project | Digital Bee Collections Network, 2014 (and updates). Version: 08 Mar 2016. National Science Foundation grant DBI 0956388 http://amnh.begoniasociety.org/dwc/AEC-DBCNet_DwC-A20160308.zip 2026-06-02T14:00:01.233Z Plant Bug Planetary Biodiversity Inventory Project PBI: Phytophagous Insects as a Model Group for Documenting Planetary Biodiversity (Insecta: Heteroptera: Miridae: Orthotylinae, Phylinae) | PBI: Phytophagous Insects as a Model Group for Documenting Planetary Biodiversity (Insecta: Heteroptera: Miridae: Orthotylinae, Phylinae). Version: 08 Mar 2016. National Science Foundation grant DBI#0316495 http://amnh.begoniasociety.org/dwc/AEC-NA_PlantBugPBI_DwC-A20160308.zip 2026-06-02T14:00:01.233Z Plants, herbivores, and parasitoids: A model system for the study of tri-trophic associations project | Tri-Trophic Thematic

Collection Network, 2014 (and updates). Version: 08 Mar 2016. <http://tcn.amnh.org/>. National Science Foundation grant(s) EF#1115081, EF#1115103, EF#1115080, EF#1115144, EF#1115191, EF#1115104, EF#1115115 http://amnh.begoniasociety.org/dwc/AEC-TTD-TCN_DwC-A20160308.zip 2026-06-02T14:00:01.233Z hash://md5/cae87918c1dffbb12bee888d9df95f3b

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 54.9MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/arthropodEasyCaptureAMNH

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/arthropodEasyCaptureAMNH \
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/arthropodEasyCaptureAMNH \
> interactions.tsv
```

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/arthropodEasyCaptureAMNH`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/arthropodEasyCaptureAMNH`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/arthropodEasyCaptureAMNH`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/arthropodEasyCaptureAMNH`)

```
# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/arthropodEasyCaptureAMNH \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that `data.zip` file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/arthropodEasyCaptureAMNH`, has fingerprint hash://md5/eae87918c1dffbb12bee888d9df95f3b, is 54.9MiB in

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

size and contains 709,968 interactions with 5 unique types of associations (e.g., interactsWith) between 8,343 primary taxa (e.g., *Lysiphlebus Lysiphlebus*) and 9,207 associated taxa (e.g., *Melilotus officinalis*).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at indexed-interactions.html.gz are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Phytocoris canescens	interactsWith	Artemisia sp.	Tri-Trophic Thematic Collection Network, 2014 (and updates). Version: 2016-03-08. http://tcn.amnh.org/ . National Science Foundation grant(s) EF#1115081, EF#1115103, EF#1115080, EF#1115144, EF#1115191, EF#1115104, EF#1115115

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Phytocoris canescens	interactsWith	Artemisia sp.	Tri-Trophic Thematic Collection Network, 2014 (and updates). Version: 2016-03-08. http://tcn.amnh.org/ . National Science Foundation grant(s) EF#1115081, EF#1115103, EF#1115080, EF#1115144, EF#1115191, EF#1115104, EF#1115115
Phytocoris canescens	interactsWith	Artemisia sp.	Tri-Trophic Thematic Collection Network, 2014 (and updates). Version: 2016-03-08. http://tcn.amnh.org/ . National Science Foundation grant(s) EF#1115081, EF#1115103, EF#1115080, EF#1115144, EF#1115191, EF#1115104, EF#1115115

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Phytocoris canescens	interactsWith	Salvia mellifera	Tri-Trophic Thematic Collection Network, 2014 (and updates). Version: 2016-03-08. http://tcn.amnh.org/ . National Science Foundation grant(s) EF#1115081, EF#1115103, EF#1115080, EF#1115144, EF#1115191, EF#1115104, EF#1115115

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
interactsWith	680488
adjacentTo	24548
hasHost	4900
parasiteOf	29
visitsFlowersOf	3

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Lysiphlebus Lysiphlebus	8085
Pygovepres vaccinicola	5913
Andrena wilkella	4808
Andrena crataegi	4379
Platycotis vittata	3545
Lygus lineolaris	3251
Aphidius Aphidius	3011

sourceTaxonName	count
Deraeocoris brevis	2863
Ophiderma flavicephala	2829
Macrosiphum Macrosiphum euphorbiae	2545
Miridae	2431
Phallospinophylus setosus	2406
Lopidea nigridia	2393
Pilophorus tibialis	2360
Aphis Aphis gossypii	2320
Myzus Nectarosiphon persicae	2299
Andrena nasonii	2244
Smilia fasciata	2178
Lasioglossum cinctipes	2154

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Melilotus officinalis	12429
Salix sp.	10754
Gossypium sp.	10105
Salix	9061
Artemisia tridentata	7839
Quercus alba	6941
Quercus sp.	6741
Pinus contorta	6240
Barbarea vulgaris	5354
Pinus ponderosa	5030
Quercus laurifolia	4672
Solidago sp.	4596
Abies procera	4470
leaves	4337
Quercus	4084
Cynodon dactylon	4082
Juniperus sp.	3938
Quercus phellos	3687
tree	3591

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Andrena wilkella	interactsWith	Melilotus officinalis	2386
Adenostomocoris pintoi	interactsWith	Adenostoma fasciculatum	1706
Vanduzea arquata	interactsWith	Robinia pseudoacacia	1604
Protoxaea gloriosa	interactsWith	Melilotus officinalis	1478
Phytocoris stellatus	interactsWith	Pinus contorta	1446
Cyrtolobus clarus	interactsWith	Quercus laurifolia	1426
Andrena arabis	interactsWith	Barbarea vulgaris	1342
Ophiderma flavicephala	interactsWith	Quercus phellos	1339
Pygovepres vaccinicola	interactsWith	Quercus douglasii	1262
Orthotylus kanakanus	interactsWith	Coprosma	1252
Cyrtolobus fuliginosus	interactsWith	Quercus falcata	1242
Andrena miserabilis	interactsWith	Salix	1216
Andrena ziziae	interactsWith	Zizia aurea	1194
Andrena crataegi	interactsWith	Physocarpus opulifolius	1178
Carneocephala triguttata nottingham	interactsWith	Cynodon dactylon	1098
Pilophorus americanus	interactsWith	Pinus contorta	1046
Plagiognathus	interactsWith	Abies procera	1020
Smilia fasciata	interactsWith	Quercus laurifolia	984
Phyllophidea picta	interactsWith	Artemisia tridentata	978

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer

to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download svg

You can download the indexed dataset under review at indexed-interactions.csv.gz. A tab-separated file can be found at indexed-interactions.tsv.gz

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration `indexed-interactions.map` :

```

MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"
  
```


Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#) 11

```

METADATA
  "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
  "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
  "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
  "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
END
CLASS
  STYLE
    COLOR          232 232 232
    OUTLINECOLOR  32 32 32
  END
END
LAYER
  NAME "indexed-interactions"
  TYPE POLYGON
  STATUS ON
  CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
  CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
  DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
      DATARANGE 0.3010299956639812 4.912747994415375
      RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
      OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
    END
  END
END

```

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Prince Maryland	NONE	col	Maryland
Mecosta Michigan	NONE	col	Michigan
Muskegon Michigan	NONE	col	Michigan
Aaronsohnia factorovskiy	SYNONYM_OF	col	Otoglyphis factorovskiy

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	1222
col	family	156
col	form	2
col	genus	1720
col	kingdom	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	order	1
col	phylum	1
col	species	12080
col	subfamily	3
col	subgenus	41
col	subspecies	501
col	subterclass	1
col	superorder	1
col	tribe	3
col	variety	134
discoverlife	NA	13998
discoverlife	species	1562
gbif	NA	836
gbif	family	157
gbif	form	5
gbif	genus	1731
gbif	kingdom	1
gbif	order	1
gbif	phylum	1
gbif	species	12302
gbif	subspecies	616
gbif	variety	322
itis	NA	5345
itis	family	149
itis	genus	1418
itis	kingdom	1
itis	order	1
itis	phylum	2
itis	species	8303
itis	subgenus	1
itis	subspecies	215
itis	superorder	1
itis	variety	141
mdd	NA	15559
ncbi	NA	6096
ncbi	clade	2
ncbi	family	143
ncbi	forma	1
ncbi	genus	1613
ncbi	order	1
ncbi	phylum	1
ncbi	section	3
ncbi	species	7619
ncbi	subfamily	2

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
ncbi	subgenus	17
ncbi	subspecies	46
ncbi	superorder	1
ncbi	tribe	2
ncbi	varietas	25
pbdb	NA	14624
pbdb	family	150
pbdb	genus	601
pbdb	kingdom	1
pbdb	order	3
pbdb	species	178
pbdb	subfamily	1
pbdb	suborder	1
pbdb	superorder	1
pbdb	tribe	1
pbdb	unranked clade	3
tpt	NA	15543
tpt	genus	15
tpt	order	1
wfo	NA	8553
wfo	family	118
wfo	form	3
wfo	genus	1243
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	section	1
wfo	species	5476
wfo	subsection	1
wfo	subspecies	150
wfo	tribe	1
wfo	variety	112
worms	NA	13364
worms	family	104
worms	genus	720
worms	kingdom	1
worms	order	1
worms	phylum	1
worms	species	1347
worms	subfamily	1
worms	subspecies	23
worms	subterclass	1
worms	superorder	1
worms	tribe	2
worms	variety	23

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	1339
col	SYNONYM_OF	9208
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	17367
discoverlife	NONE	18397
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1441
discoverlife	SYNONYM_OF	460
discoverlife	HOMONYM_OF	43
gbif	NONE	895
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	9443
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	19574
itis	NONE	5892
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	12830
itis	SYNONYM_OF	1681
mdd	NONE	19948
ncbi	NONE	6549
ncbi	SAME_AS	12905
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	854
ncbi	COMMON_NAME_OF	2
pbdb	NONE	17673
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	2281
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	66
tpt	NONE	19927
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	21
wfo	NONE	10380
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	8049
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	2579
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	889
worms	NONE	15826
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	4270
worms	SYNONYM_OF	639

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T11:24:38Z	summary	https://github.com/globalbioticinteractions/arthropod
2026-06-03T11:24:38Z	summary	709968 interaction(s)
2026-06-03T11:24:38Z	summary	0 note(s)
2026-06-03T11:24:38Z	summary	6 info(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-03) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

filename	description
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map

filename	description
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads

filename	description
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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